

Split-component signal transduction systems

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Running title: Split-component signal transduction systems

Keywords: cell signaling, gasocrine signaling, ligand-receptor, gasoreceptor

How cells and organisms communicate with each other is a fundamental question in biology. Recently, when I proposed the term "swodkoreceptor" for all the sugar-sensing proteins, I proposed glucokinase regulator GCKR (also known as GKRP, glucokinase regulatory protein) as a swodkoreceptor that senses fructose 1-phosphate and fructose 6-phosphate, and glucokinase as one of its signal transducers.^{1,2} However, this signaling cannot be referred to as an one- or two- or co- or multi-component signal transduction systems.³⁻⁵ The criteria for co-component signal transduction must either be relaxed or a new term must be created. Therefore, I propose the term "split-component signal transduction system". Exploring split-component signal transduction systems based on proteins (receptors) and nucleic acids (riboceptors or deoxyriboceptors) in gasocrine, thermocrine, aquacrine, swodkocrine, sonocrine, and photocrine signaling can help us identify and understand novel cell signaling mechanisms. Finally, in addition to proteins and nucleic acids, other classes of biomolecules must also be considered as both signaling molecules and signal generators.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Savani Anbalagan: conceptualization, writing of the original draft, and review and editing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author thank Zofia Szweykowska-Kulinska (Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan, Poland) for allowing him to attend her inspiring lectures on molecular evolution. The author also thank Agnieszka Chacinska (Past affiliation: Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw, Regenerative Mechanisms for Health - International Research Agendas Programme and current affiliation: International Institute of Molecular Machines and Mechanisms, Polish Academy of Science, Warsaw, Poland) for suggesting him to attend the 44th FEBS Congress meeting. The author is supported by National Science Centre grants (SONATA-BIS 2020/38/E/NZ3/00090 and SONATA 2021/43/D/NZ3/01798).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

The funding agency and institution S.A. is affiliated with was not involved in the contents of the manuscript.

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